

Primary Class Students Technology Lessons through Manners Rules Based on Bring Up Ways

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Abstract: Etiquette morality is a person decoration Polite, knowledgeable, hardworking, faithful a child not only parents, maybe whole of society the most big wealth. Indeed, everyone a child personality in the family is formed. So, the family is perfect generation foundation is considered In the family not only in society children moral and legal in terms of education, especially justice, duty, patriotism formation, mother homeland to love feeling wake up very important is considered.

Keywords: Etiquette, morals, family, faith, decoration, justice, duty, mother, homeland, duty, offense, spiritual and moral principle, affection, discipline.

Definition of the concepts of manners, behavior, ethics.

Ethics and - society , time , humanity history for example be will receive positive behavior is the sum . **Manners** are human about nice impression rousing , but community , society and humanity so much in his life important important have non-existent , national to traditions based on beautiful behavior own into I can . **Behavior** - family , community , neighborhood scale important was , but society and humanity to his life significant effect does not show nice human of behavior set

Ethical education as a result decency-to good manners , good manners - high to morality what has become as , moral education to the road not placed in the place certain person , time from decency - to ugliness , from ugliness - to ugliness pass can So and ethics this three moral event each other with in unity and in relativity learns Education basis many p in terms of to knowledge and to the good ones in approach and their instructive life style based on surface to the rich experience that came and purmano words where level to know go horseshoes it is In this place , my grandfather in my youth said beautiful their training example as I would like to quote : "My son, our scholars left wise word and materials how much to memorize if you go , to your heart so much patterned keeps going As a result , your so is your tongue nice hall words get fat begins ." Our children are also stories and instructive to words very they need

Primary class technology lessons through students manners rules based on bring up important technology as a creative discipline students manners within education in finding big the ground creates Education in the process the children manners rules based on brought up to go important importance occupation this is it the rules decisions and principles based on will improve .

1. General medium education of the institution internal order and manners rules Uzbekistan Republic of Constitution , " Education about " , " To the youth about state policy " , "Child 's

rights guarantees about ”, “ Adult not enough between lack of control and of offenses prevention about ”, “ Information freedom principles and guarantees about”. Laws and Ministers " Perfect generation in education family institute and of citizens himself himself manage bodies education institutions with mutually cooperation more development measures about". decision and generally accepted done spiritual and moral principles based on work developed

2. Internal order rules - general medium education in the institution employees and students by to education about regulatory and legal in the documents and institution In the charter set placed education in the process compliance to be done a must has been order and rules . Manners rules - general medium education in the institution national and universal values based on employees , students and parents for defined behavior standards .

3. This internal order and manners rules common medium education of the institution spiritual and educational direction activity with depends main principles own into takes and common medium education institution team and students compliance reach for mandatory is considered

4. General medium education of the institution internal order and manners rules (next in places – Rules) education institution management , pedagogue and technical employees (next in places - team members) and students , their parents (or their place clicker persons) for mutually in relationships manners , behavior standards minimum requirements determines

5. This Rules common medium education in the institution (next in places - education institution) education and education mutually harmony provide , teacher position inviolability confession reach , friendly environment create , readers by study program successful mastery , man and his rights respect increase , manners and communication culture to develop directed .

6. This Rules People education ministry at the disposal of education in institutions app is done , non-state and another education institutions for recommended to the feature have

7. Rules current from doing goal education in the institution healthy socio-psychological environment formation , to students time requirements and national values based on education give , person and his rights respect to do , manners and communication culture development , high spiritual and moral qualities formation , students health storage , education institution property , education equipment and employees safety to provide possibility giving friendly environment from creating consists of

8. Rules the team of members education institution in the area , lesson and from class except training , break in times of education and education with depends at events themselves to keep in order that puts norms is considered

9. This the rules the team members and students for education institution in the area mandatory is considered

10. To the rules action to do on the surface public , parents , education institutions pedagogue employees between social networks through wide propaganda will be done .

Above given manners rules each one person for discipline as action because it does city doorman it's not as if each one of action account , answer yes , of course . In the family children own duty loyalty in the spirit bring up responsibility parents , society with breathless being , consciousness , conscience such as qualities with closely depends . In this case, the parents mutually sincere relationship , their their children with close , friendly in relation to be , their future dreams and goals understand to get , of children healthy - health adult reach for basis will be Man education in the process good behavior , habits and intelligence factors have was if so , life lessons so much good understands and good things done increases and on the contrary , how much upbringing little , vital if there are few skills , such person sometimes

knowing or not knowing bad to work hand hits In society, the child is his own place to find for both parents and teachers are responsible is common medium education education in institutions continue bringing will go Not only that lessons during conversations , meetings , events , auditions through manners rules by teaching in practice supporting to go to efficiency reach pledge being service does

None when the children in education road placed from mistakes the eye that we do not close need Current in our marriage some one rude , uneducated , unintelligent , addicted to drugs , to his parents hand to raise and own of children unhappy to live cause happening people occurs . Such appear to be main cause parents ? His child human behavior to his actions their to education indifferences reason was Good education , some as thought , one hourly or one daily work it's not . Purposeful education from the educator Endurance , tenacity , big knowledge and requires experience . So, every one parents , teachers to education about knowledge and to qualification have to be it's a must big requires responsibility and experience .

Children in education quickly positive to the results reach for to them knowledge to give with together , it is known work processes attraction achievement , occupation and secrets of specialization added to teach to the goal is appropriate . Education of work sometimes ineffective to be main of reasons one education in the process of discipline is not to be . Person how much love and discipline based on if brought up , it's bad behavior from actions so much long will be Education main purpose young people happy , own of the time Dear , respected and selfless person by doing from upbringing consists of

Education complexity is that he never when does not end , that is person from birth to death until necessary will be From this except , one education saw generation instead of came children again again from the head education to do needed will be And this education relentlessly periodicity and eternity shows to the teachings of Islam See , child parents in charge of deposit they are this deposit about are responsible . Children education neglect huge error , deposit betrayal and person of religion is a defect . Parents of his child the first are coaches . Quran in my car family to the people of attention how much necessity Allah may Allah bless him and grant him peace so statement says : " Hey believers , you yourselves and your family members firewood people and stones has been from hell save it , on it (hell) . tough and God is strict to themselves ordered to something disobedience who does not , only to themselves ordered thing who does angels turur ” (Tahrim , verse 6) Any education , in particular advice in the family starts The main goal of education is each other compassionate people adult is to deliver . Father and mothers again don't forget that today their children education attention did not give person from years after that , without a home , without a family remains .

Abu Hamid Ghazali a child upbringing about so thoughts means : "Know! Child education the most important is one of the works . The child is the father and to mother deposit A child's heart pure , delicate , simple and each how pattern and from the photo free is a gem . To him how pattern if placed , accordingly formed , eaten towards bends If the child is good Good to learn inside adult enough , the world and hereafter happiness finds Of course this to merit his parents , teacher and to him education gave each one person is a partner . If the child is careless leave it's bad if you put it inside grow up , to misery face holds and death will be This is a sin load that's it cry of parents undertake will be loaded . In this regard Allah may Allah bless him and grant him peace Believers , you yourselves and people your families from hell keep it ," he warns .

Education two basis have : virtue guarding beautiful ethics and naughty out of the way , bad to the situation from falling which keeps vigilance . Father and child the world from the fire how much protection if he does , the hereafter from the fire more than that protection act need Etiquette education by means of good behaviors to teach , from evils to return , to abundance

do not get used to it , adornment love do not wake up with father his child hereafter from the fire preserves

Child education how much early education begins result so much efficient will be Because early in age them goodness towards twist ease with will pass From lack of education to the body came bad behavior and habits later on again bring up way with correction can But that's it for many p work spend to do right will come

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